

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

Deliverable D2.3

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable provides additional details regarding the Trial Network Lifecycle from the foundation defined in D2.2. Moreover, it provides an overview on Data Reusability concept and defines the 6G-SANDBOX strategy on this topic. Finally, it provides a study on 6G Stakeholders and details the collaborations of the Project Consortium with external entities.

The deliverable is organized into five chapters: introduction, Trial Network's lifecycle, Data Reusability, stakeholders and collaborations, and a concluding summary. Its target audience spans from the project consortium and the research community to funding agencies and the public.

The content of this deliverable ensures validation of objectives, alignment among stakeholders, and transparency in the technological advancements, and it is also laying the foundation for achieving the expected outcomes of the 6G-SANDBOX project.

KEYWORDS

Trial Network, Trial Network Lifecycle, Data Reusability, 6G Stakeholders, Open Call, Platform, Facility, Experimentation, 6G-SANDBOX.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is produced as part of Work Package 2 “Ecosystem Analysis and 6G-SANDBOX Facility design”, particularly detailing the work performed on Task 2.2 “Trial Networks Lifecycle and stakeholders analysis”. It builds upon the contents of Deliverable D2.2 “Final overall framework design and requirements” **Error! Reference source not found.** and is consistent with the architecture described in it, while providing additional details on the components that implement the Trial Network lifecycle. In addition to this, the document includes an analysis on trends and considerations taken by the Consortium with regards to the improvement of experimental data (results) reusability. Finally, the document describes the efforts taken to increase the reach of the 6G-SANDBOX Project, including the identification of interested stakeholders, the engagement strategy, and a report on existing collaborations with other entities.

It is important to note that this deliverable centers on design aspects. The implementation of the components that support the required functionality for such design will be reported as part of WP4, in Deliverable D4.2 “Integration and Management of 6G trial networks - Final report”, due on month 30 (June 2025).

1.2 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The document is structured in five chapters: This introductory chapter shortly describes the intention and content of the deliverable. Chapter 2 centers on the updated definition of the Trial Network lifecycle, and the design of the components that ultimately support this functionality in the 6G-SANDBOX facilities. Chapter 3 describes several ongoing initiatives for enhancing data reusability and expose common patterns in them, which are then used for defining small updates to the 6G-SANDBOX architecture, with the intention of better supporting this goal. Chapter 4 includes an analysis of the stakeholders involved in the Project, the guidelines for interacting with third parties and a description of several past and ongoing collaborations. Finally, Chapter 5 presents the conclusions of this document.

1.3 TARGET AUDIENCE

This deliverable is public and available to any individuals and communities; however, several target audiences have been considered specially during its production:

- The Project Consortium in itself, to clearly document:
 - o The details, rationale and design decisions behind the Trial Network’s lifecycle, and the handling of results. These details guides the implementation performed in WP4, towards the required functionality to support such design within the 6G-SANDBOX architecture.
 - o The stakeholders and engagement strategy of the Consortium, including information on previous efforts, that can act as guidelines for future collaborations with external entities.
- The Research Community and funding agency (the European Commission), summarizing the goals and scope and expected functionality of the Trial Networks, the considerations taken for improving data reusability, aligning the Project with ongoing European initiatives in the matter, and to present the strategies and existing collaborations that further increase the reach and continuity of the work performed in 6G-SANDBOX.
- The public, ensuring awareness and transparency of the work performed by the Project Consortium.

2 TRIAL NETWORK LIFECYCLE

2.1 DESCRIPTION AND DESIGN

Trial Networks serve as isolated and configurable environments where different 6G network components and technologies can be tested and validated before deployment in real-world scenarios.

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the Trial Network lifecycle, covering its design, components, architecture, validation process and implementation. It also details the Trial Network Lifecycle Manager (TNLCM), which plays a central role in automating the lifecycle management of these networks, and the 6G Library, which describes the components that can be part of a Trial Network.

By leveraging TNLCM, experimenters can define Trial Networks through **descriptors**, specifying the required network components and their interconnections. The system ensures a seamless transition between different lifecycle states, handling resource allocation, configuration, and eventual decommissioning.

On the other hand, the 6G Library containerizes the description of each particular component, allowing them to be developed independently from each other and from the TNLCM.

Figure 1: 6G Library and TNLCM roles

The following sub-sections cover:

- Trial Network Design: covers the conceptualization and structure of a Trial Network.
- Trial Network Descriptors: explains how TNs are defined and the components they include.
- General Trial Network Architecture: details the fundamental building blocks and interconnections.
- Lifecycle and State Management: describes the different states a Trial Network can go through and how transitions are managed.
- Validation Process: outlines the steps required to ensure the correct deployment and operation of a TN.
- TNLCM and 6G Library overview: Additional details on the design of these two components.

2.1.1 TRIAL NETWORK DESCRIPTORS. COMPONENTS AND INTERCONNECTIONS.

A Trial Network is deployed from a descriptor file, in which its components are defined using the YAML syntax. This file has .yaml extension and its content specifies the different elements that make up the network, as well as their relationships and configurations.

Within the 6G-Library, the input parameters allowed for each component are established, ensuring a coherent and compatible structure with the system. These parameters determine aspects such as connectivity, network configuration and resources required for deployment.

The generic structure of a descriptor file [2] follows the format below:

```

trial_network: # Mandatory, contains the description of all entities in the Trial Network
type-name: # Mandatory, entity name. Unique identifier for each entity in the Trial Network
type: # Mandatory, 6G-Library component type
name: # Mandatory, custom name.
debug: # Optional, param to debug component in Jenkins.
dependencies: # Mandatory, list of dependencies of the component with other components
- type-name
- ...
input: # Mandatory, dictionary with the variables collected from the input part of the 6G-Library
key: value
    
```

An example of a valid descriptor file can be seen in Annex 1. In this example, the Trial Network Descriptor is composed by the following components:

- **tn_init**: provides a VXLAN and a bastion, facilitating access to the Trial Network through a VPN.
- **vnet-internal**: defines an internal private network used by the oneKE to be deployed later.
- **oneKE-cluster**: deploys a Kubernetes cluster. Connects to vnet-internal via the one_oneKE_internal_vnet: "vnet-internal" input field.
- **open5gs_k8s-core**: deploys the Open5GS core inside the Kubernetes cluster. Connects to oneKE-cluster via the one_open5gs_k8s_target input field: "oneKE-cluster".
- **ueransim-gnb**: simulates a gNodeB (gNB), the radio access node in a 5G network, linked to the Open5GS core. It connects to open5gs_k8s-core via the input field one_ueransim_gnb_linked_open5gs: "open5gs_k8s-core".
- **ueransim-ue**: simulates a user device (UE, User Equipment) that connects to the previously declared gNB. It is linked to ueransim-gnb via the input field one_ueransim_ue_linked_gnb: "ueransim-gnb".

2.1.2 GENERAL TRIAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURE, BASIC COMPONENTS.

The fundamental component of any Trial Network is **tn_init**, which is **mandatory**. This component serves as the foundation for the entire network and acts as a bridge between its core infrastructure and external access mechanisms.

tn_init is composed of two essential subcomponents from the **6G-Library**:

- **tn_vxlan**: responsible for establishing a virtual network (VXLAN) to interconnect the different elements of the Trial Network securely.
- **tn_bastion**: provides secure access to the network via VPN, ensuring controlled and authenticated entry points for users.

Since **tn_init** is a required component, every Trial Network descriptor must start with the following section:

```

trial_network:
  tn_init:
    type: "tn_init"
    dependencies: []
    input: {}
    
```

This structure ensures that all Trial Networks have a standardized initialization process, allowing seamless integration with other components. The `tn_init` component guarantees secure network isolation and remote accessibility, which are essential for managing and testing experimental network environments.

2.2 TRIAL NETWORK LIFECYCLE MANAGER

2.2.1 INTRODUCTION

The Trial Network Lifecycle Manager (TNLCM) is a tool developed in Python to manage the entire lifecycle of trial networks in research and development environments. It automates the processes of validation, deployment, monitoring, suspension and deletion of trial networks, ensuring efficient and scalable resource management.

Python was chosen as the implementation language for its readability, rich ecosystem and flexibility, allowing seamless integration with databases, APIs, and external systems. Its extensive community support ensures maintainability and scalability for future developments.

2.2.2 TRIAL NETWORK STATES AND TRANSITION PROCESS.

A Trial Network goes through multiple states during its lifecycle, including validation deployment, suspension, and eventual removal. These states define the different phases a trial network can go through, ensuring proper management and control over its resources.

Each Trial Network can exist in one of the following **states**:

- **Validated**: the trial network descriptor is checked to determine if it can be deployed. The **6G-Library** is used for validation.
- **Activated**: the trial network has been successfully deployed in OpenNebula and is ready for use.
- **Suspended**: the trial network has been temporarily suspended. In such case, it remains deployed but is turned off.
- **Failed**: meaning that an error occurred during the trial network deployment process.
- **Destroyed**: the trial network deployment in OpenNebula has been removed, but its content is still stored in the database and locally.
- **Purge**: the trial network and its associated callbacks are completely removed from the database, along with its local content.

The state transitions define how a trial network progresses through its lifecycle:

- **Initial state → Validated**: the trial network descriptor has been successfully validated and is ready for deployment.
- **Validated → Activated**: the trial network is deployed and ready for use.
- **Validated → Failed**: deployment failed due to an error.
- **Validated → Purge**: the trial network is invalid and removed from the system.
- **Failed → Failed**: deployment attempt failed again.
- **Activated → Destroyed**: the trial network is destroyed and can be deployed again later.
- **Activated → Suspended**: *(TODO: Implementation pending)*
- **Suspended → Activated**: *(TODO: Implementation pending)*
- **Destroyed → Activated**: the trial network is redeployed and ready for use.
- **Destroyed → Purge**: the trial network is completely removed.

These states and transitions ensure that the **TNLCM** properly manages each trial network, keeping track of its status and handling failures or re-deployments efficiently. The overall flow, including the states as mentioned above, is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Possible Trial Network states and transitions.

2.2.3 TRIAL NETWORK VALIDATION PROCESS.

The validation process ensures that a Trial Network descriptor file is correctly structured and that its components are properly interconnected before deployment.

The first version of the validation process includes the following checks:

- The descriptor follows the generic structure defined in Section 2.1.1.
- All the components are correctly interconnected. This is verified based on the definitions provided in the `.tnlcm/core.yaml` file of the 6G-Library, which specifies the expected connections for each component.

Plans are in place to enhance the validation process by integrating Pydantic, a Python library that provides robust data validation and schema enforcement. This integration will allow for stricter validation rules, better error handling, and improved maintainability of the validation logic.

2.3 6G LIBRARY

2.3.1 INTRODUCTION

Historically, deploying network components required manual configuration by specialized engineers, siloed scripts and documentation that were hard to keep updated and difficulty synchronizing changes across multiple environments (development, test, production). These traditional approaches become unsustainable in the context of 6G networks. This was the driving force behind creating the 6G Library, offering a more modular and automated pathway.

Research and development towards 6G often involves a wide variety of technologies, protocols, and vendors. In the context of 6G-SANDBOX we define a Trial Network as a fully configurable, manageable and controllable environment, that combines virtual and physical components to model a 6G network environment where it is possible to execute experiments to obtain many kinds of results.

6G-SANDBOX project, defines and provides Trial Networks, as flexible and configurable networks that combine components to validate 6G technologies. These networks are versatile in terms of technologies, components, experimental processes, and target metrics. The catalogue of components is driven by the 6G-SANDBOX library.

So, to be able to compose a Trial Network it is necessary to have available a catalog of building blocks that can be used to create the environment, and it should contain physical and virtual equipment that can be used to design the network architecture to run an experiment.

Thus, in this context, the **6G-SANDBOX Library** is the catalog of building blocks. It is an open-source initiative aimed at simplifying and standardizing the definition, provision, and management of the components in Trial Network environments.

The library is a catalog of building blocks that we can put together to model the Trial Network.

Building Block = Component

The library has been designed following a set of basic principles: simplicity, collaboration, extensibility, versioning and ease of use. Consequently, each library component follows the same philosophy. The library has been developed following the Everything as Code approach (EaC), meaning every component is self-contained and includes all the necessary scripts and automation tools for deployment on a 6G-SANDBOX platform.

The objectives and goals of the 6G-SANDBOX library are:

- **Reusability:** To provide a library where each 6G component (e.g. core network, traffic simulator, user equipment, etc.) is self-contained and can be easily replicated.
- **Enhance Collaboration:** To host the library on a Git repository (GitHub) to invite feedback, bug reports, and feature suggestions from a broader community.
- **Ensure Consistency:** To use the EaC mindset and keep all environments consistent, documented, and version controlled.
- **Accelerate Innovation:** By removing the overhead of repetitive manual tasks, developers and researchers can focus on advancing 6G features rather than wrestling with infrastructure setup.

These objectives fit perfectly with key principles of adopting EaC approach

EaC is a modern software development principle that extends the concept of Infrastructure as Code (IaC) to encompass all aspects of the software development lifecycle. This approach aims to improve efficiency, consistency, and collaboration across teams by

EaC

Everything as Code

}

- Infrastructure
- Configuration
- Documentation
- Reports
- Pipelines

treating every component of the software ecosystem as code. Some common examples of EaC include aC, Configuration as Code (CaC), and declarative pipelines (PaC).

Moreover, to ensure consistency when creating and integrating these components, a set of requirements has been established that 6G-SANDBOX library components must meet to be integrated properly with the rest of the 6G-SANDBOX platform.

- *Version Control:* All components, including infrastructure, configuration, and application code, are stored in version control systems like Git (GitHub in our case). This enables tracking changes, collaborating effectively, and maintaining a single source of truth.

- *Automation*: Processes are automated through scripts and tools, reducing manual interventions and human errors. This includes building processes, testing, deployment, and infrastructure provisioning.
- *Declarative Definitions*: Resources and configurations are defined declaratively, specifying the desired end state rather than the steps to achieve it. This approach enhances readability and maintainability.
- *Idempotency*: Operations can be repeated multiple times without changing the result beyond the initial application. This ensures consistency and reliability in the system.
- *Modularity and Reusability*: Code is organized into modular, reusable components, promoting consistency across projects and reducing duplication of effort.
- *Consistency*: By defining EaC, teams can ensure consistent environments across development, testing, and production.
- *Auditability*: Changes are tracked and versioned, providing a clear audit trail for compliance and troubleshooting purposes.
- *Disaster Recovery*: Infrastructure and configurations can be quickly recreated in case of failures, improving resilience and reducing downtime.

By adopting EaC principles, 6G-SANDBOX collaborators can streamline their library components' development processes, improve collaboration between teams, and create a more reliable and scalable platform.

2.3.2 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY RELATIONSHIPS

The 6G-SANDBOX library is hosted on a Git repository¹. In this subsection, the focus is on the integrations that exist between other components of the platform and the library.

Figure 3: Main components supporting the Trial Network's lifecycle

As we have mentioned, each library component is self-contained. This means that hold information about public metadata, private metadata and automations (IaC, CaC, PaC).

Public metadata can be consumed by third party players via a web portal from which an experimenter can query the information of each component and use it to develop a Trial Network.

The private metadata is then used by the TNLCM to compose and validate the Trial Network descriptor. The TNLCM then triggers the deployment of each component through Jenkins pipelines as code (PaC) using this descriptor.

Jenkins makes use of files that describe automation for infrastructure deployment (IaC), infrastructure configuration (CaC) and sometimes additional automation through the execution of auxiliary scripts (Bash).

The 6G library becomes the single source of truth and every time it is updated, the rest of the integrated components have access to the latest changes.

¹ <https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library>

2.3.3 6G LIBRARY TECHNOLOGY STACK

From the beginning of the project, it was decided to limit the number of tools that make up the technology stack. The purpose of this limitation was to select only the most known and recognized tools in the industry, with the premise of being open source, so that all the components of the library were designed following the same principles and structure, facilitating collaboration between developers creating reusable blocks of code.

The categories of tools that are considered necessary:

- Virtual infrastructure management: Terraform
- Configuration management: Ansible
- Job orchestrator: Jenkins
- General purpose: Bash scripts

Figure 4: 6G Library Technology Stack

2.3.3.1 TERRAFORM FOR INFRASTRUCTURE AS CODE (IAC)

Terraform is an open-source IaC tool that allows you to define, provision, and manage infrastructure resources across multiple cloud providers (OpenNebula, Vmware, AWS, Azure, etc...). It serves to automate the creation and management of infrastructure in a declarative manner, facilitating consistent and reproducible deployment of complex environments.

The advantages of using this tool for infrastructure management are:

- **Declarative Syntax:** One can describe the desired state (e.g., “I want 2 VMs in this subnet”), and Terraform figures out how to reach that state from the current one.
- **Cross-Platform Flexibility:** Terraform supports major cloud providers (AWS, Azure, GCP) and on-premises solutions, meaning the 6G-SANDBOX Library can be used in a wide range of environments (if the components are developed to be compatible with multiple cloud providers).
- **Consistent Environments:** By having .tf files to deploy each library component, we ensure uniform deployments. If a new developer checks out the code and runs terraform apply, they get the same infrastructure.

2.3.3.2 ANSIBLE FOR CONFIGURATION MANAGEMENT (CAC)

Ansible is an open-source automation tool that simplifies configuration management, application deployment, and task automation across multiple systems. It serves to streamline IT operations by using a simple, human-readable language to define and execute tasks, enabling efficient management of complex infrastructures without requiring agents on remote systems.

The advantages of using this tool for configurations management are:

- **Agentless:** There is no need to install additional software on every target machine; Ansible connects via SSH, reducing overhead.
- **Readable YAML Playbooks:** YAML syntax is more approachable for describing tasks, roles, and configurations.
- **Idempotent Execution:** Running the same playbook multiple times ensures the system remains in the desired state, which is crucial for large-scale 6G environments with frequent updates.

2.3.3.3 JENKINS FOR ORCHESTRATION (PAC)

Jenkins is an open-source automation server that facilitates the execution of workflows, that can be modeled with a declarative language on regular text files and also is robust tools for managing and monitoring executions.

The advantages of using this tool for orchestration are:

- **Declarative Pipelines:** Jenkins allows developers to define pipelines using its scripting language, enabling the creation of sophisticated, multi-stage workflows.
- **Centralized Control:** It serves as a centralized server for automating various tasks, allowing developers to focus on other work while pipelines run.
- **Real-time Monitoring:** Jenkins offers detailed reports on build and deployment metrics, enabling teams to identify trends and optimize workflows.
- **Scalability:** Whether dealing with small projects or large enterprise applications, Jenkins can be configured to meet specific

2.3.3.4 BASH SCRIPTS FOR CUSTOM TASKS

Finally, Bash is a command-line interface shell program and scripting language used primarily to interact directly with the operating system, execute commands, automate tasks, and create scripts for complex operations. We will use Bash to complement those actions that cannot be executed with Terraform or Ansible.

The advantages of using this tool are:

- **Simplicity:** Bash is ubiquitous on Linux systems.
- **Rapid Prototyping:** Often tasks arise that don't fit neatly into Terraform or Ansible, like a quick performance check, running a custom data-plane test, or checking logs.
- **Flexibility:** Scripts can be called manually or integrated into CI/CD pipelines, bridging the gap between system-level commands and higher-level orchestration tools.

With the combination of these four tools, we have all the necessary capabilities to model self-contained 6G-SANDBOX library components.

2.3.4 BENEFITS OF THE GIT-CENTRIC APPROACH

Git is a version control system used for tracking changes in files. It is generally used for source code management in software development. Using a Git repository (project GitHub² in this case), to host the 6G library code, allows us to take advantage of multiple features that Git offers out of the box.

Figure 5: Different branches on the 6G Library repository

² <https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library>

Hosting the project on a Git repository (GitHub) enables:

- **Transparent History:** Each commit includes a record of what changed and why. If a configuration breaks something, we can pinpoint the change or revert to a known working version.
- **Branching for new components or features:** We can spin up new branches to test out new 6G components without disrupting the main branch.
- **Pull Request Workflows:** Proposed changes can be reviewed, discussed, and tested before they're merged, ensuring higher quality and collective ownership of the codebase.
- **Traceability:** View commits, diffs, and associated timestamps. Identify the contributor and the reasoning behind each change (via commit messages or pull request discussions). This level of traceability is incredibly valuable for auditing, compliance, and knowledge transfer.

Because the repository is public, external experts, researchers, or anyone can:

- **Propose Improvements:** Suggest better ways to implement or structure certain automations.
- **Report Issues:** Quickly alert maintainers to any bugs or documentation gaps.
- **Contribute New Components:** As 6G matures, new modules or expansions (e.g., integrating new radio technologies) can be added by anyone.

2.3.5 CONCLUSION

The **6G-SANDBOX Library** is more than just a set of scripts, it is a strategy for tackling the complexity of next-generation network components by:

- **Centralizing** definitions in a publicly accessible Git repository
- **Leveraging** Terraform, Ansible, and bash for a holistic EaC approach
- **Embracing** modular, folder-based organization

With this approach, a team is empowered to deploy reliable, consistent, and easily auditable Trial Networks. The open-source nature of the project fosters a dynamic community around 6G development, where knowledge is shared, and standards can emerge organically.

Ultimately, the goal is to **accelerate innovation** in 6G by removing infrastructural bottlenecks and letting researchers, developers, and operators focus on what truly matters, pioneering the future of wireless connectivity.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS REUSABILITY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

To be effective, the results generated as part of an experimentation process need to be recorded in a way that allows for the study of the data at a later state. These results must be identifiable and organized so that meaningful conclusions can be extracted from the raw data. However, in many cases these results are stored using a non-standardized format that only allows the original researchers to perform such analysis and are effectively discarded once the initial research has been concluded.

To enable reusability of experimental data, it is necessary to improve this approach. Meaningful metadata are added to the results, making them searchable and filterable, and storing them as standardized datasets in repositories where they can be made available for researchers and other third parties.

3.2 ORIGINAL SUPPORT

The 6G-SANDBOX experimentation approach foresees the organization of the results generated by an experiment, including the specification of a limited set of metadata. More specifically, all the experiments

executed using the orchestration tools provided in the 6G Library, can be tagged with a unique (per Trial Network) execution ID and auxiliary metadata ("Slice", "Scenario", "TestCases" and "Notes"). To improve filtering and searchability, these tools store the generated results in different locations (measurements, akin to tables in a database) and fields (like columns in a database), with each independent result including the timestamp in which it was generated.

3.3 ANALYSIS AND COLLABORATIONS

3.3.1 OPEN-ACCESS REPOSITORIES - ZENODO

As part of the effort to enable the access to the experimentation results by the community, several data repositories have emerged, following the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). These open-access repositories store datasets from heterogeneous research topics using well-defined, standardized formats along with the metadata required for allowing external users to find suitable data for their research.

Moreover, these repositories maximize the usability of experimental results beyond the original research that generated them. They allow heterogeneous approaches to be applied to the study of the same data, potentially decoupling the generation of data from its study, and generally improve the collaboration and advancement of research.

In particular, the Zenodo [3] repository, which is the successor of the OpenAIRE Orphan Records Repository created as a result of the OpenAIRE Horizon 2020 project [4], is already being used by the 6G-SANDBOX consortium to provide open access to the community for several results. At the time of writing, the 6G-SANDBOX community [5] contains 16 resources, including 4 datasets.

3.3.2 TMV WORKING GROUP

The TMV (Testing, Measuring and Validation) WG is an SNS-JU working group, led by the 6G-SANBOX Project Coordinator Micheal Dieudonne, focuses on promoting commonalities across projects that have strong interest in Testing & Monitoring (T&M) methodologies. The former provides a forum to share the best practices to support 6G Trial use cases, including the development of test and measurement methods, test cases, procedures, as well as the KPIs/KVIs formalization and validation to the greatest possible extent, to ensure a unique European vision on how the entire lifecycle of the 6G network, ranging from R&D to actual deployed environments, can be supported.

The TMV WG is made up of 3 sub-WGs: the KPI Definition and Monitoring sub-WG, the KVI Estimation sub-WG, and the Test Data reusability sub-WG. In particular, the latter was established by 6G-SANDBOX in March 2024, as a platform for SNS-JU cross-project collaboration concerning the identification of a common data management framework which enables experimental and data reusability, not only within a single given project but spanning multiple SNS-JU research initiatives. The adoption of a common data management framework would address the current need for each SNS-JU project to design and implement its own dedicate framework, which is both inefficient, and actively hindering cross-project data reusability.

With this goal in mind, the Test Data reusability sub-WG performed a preliminary analysis of 3 different data management initiatives, GAIA-X, Eclipse, and SLICES, which were considered as potential solutions for the standardisation of data management across SNS-JU projects. GAIA-X and Eclipse were ruled out early on, due to lack of interest from most of the sub-WG in their functionality. Instead, SLICES was deemed of interest and was thus investigated further by the sub-WG. The SLICES project presented their work to the TMV Test Data reusability sub-WG, and each project was given the choice of testing the data management framework, for the purposes of potential standardisation across the SNS-JU. Following these discussions, 6G-SANDBOX has decided to adopt the SLICES framework, as discussed in Section 3.3.3. This decision is partly motivated by the long-term nature of the initiative, which is planned to continue well beyond the duration of the 6G-SANDBOX project, thus potentially representing a mature framework for future European research projects as well. The adoption of

SLICES in 6G-SANDBOX has been also considered by the SUNRISE-6G project, with additional SNS-JU projects expected to follow. Up to now, only one of the projects participating to the TMV Test Data reusability sub-WG, i.e., 6G-BRICKS, decided to not adopt SLICES since the project is in its final stages.

6G-SANDBOX will continue to drive the adoption of SLICES within the SNS-JU, with the belief that it will represent a significant boon to cross-project data sharing and experiment reusability. Moreover, the TMV Test Data reusability sub-WG will continue to report on its efforts with SLICES and provide feedback to the SLICES initiative with the goal of promoting its standardisation with European research.

3.3.3 SLICES INTEROPERABILITY FRAMEWORK.

The 6G-SANDBOX consortium entered in contact with the SLICES-PP H2020 project [6], to study the possibility of adopting the SLICES MRS (Metadata Registry System) as part of the 6G-SANDBOX architecture and workflow, allowing the reusability of the results generated by the experimentation platforms in a standardized way and using rich metadata. To that effect, several meetings between representatives of both consortiums took place.

SLICES-PP has allowed access to the code and elements necessary for the deployment of local instances of the SLICES MRS (the SLICES Mini DMI standalone). The provided package has been deployed in the premises of the Málaga Platform, and at the time of writing it is being tested. As a result of these trials several improvements have been identified and issues detected. These findings are then communicated back to the SLICES project, which is using the information provided to enhance the system.

3.3.4 DATA SPACES.

Data Spaces is an ongoing European initiative for the creation of a single market for data and is part of the European Data Strategy [7] defined in the year 2020. The main objective of this initiative is the creation of a unified, interoperable market for data, that follows, from its inception, the European rules for data protection, privacy and competition.

A data space is a federated data ecosystem where the different instances share common rules and policies. Different data spaces make use of compatible infrastructure and governance frameworks, with the following key characteristics:

- A data space shall make use of the secure underlying IT infrastructure that is able to preserve the privacy of all the stakeholders involved.
- Defines a clear data governance mechanism, with transparent rules that determine the rights of each stakeholder and is compliant with existing European legislation.
- Gives full control to data holders for defining the conditions in which the data they voluntarily provide (for free or against remuneration) can be accessed or used.
- It is open to individuals or organizations without discrimination of any participant.

The European Commission, through the creation and funding of the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) [8], contributes to the creation of sovereign data spaces. The DSSC aims to address the organizational and technical matters required for the creation of data spaces, including the creation of building blocks and blueprints, the definition of best practices and reference implementations. Any organization can receive support from the DSSC for the creation of interoperable data spaces, becoming part of the community.

3.4 SELECTED METHODOLOGY AND ARCHITECTURE UPDATES.

As can be seen in the previous sub-sections, data reusability is an open issue that several initiatives are trying to tackle independently with different solutions, however an interest in standardized formats coupled with rich metadata is a common pattern in all of them. Considering that this approach, though less formalized, was already taken into consideration in the 6G-SANDBOX architecture and methodology, it is possible to reuse several existing components and make the required extensions for supporting these existing and emerging solutions.

The updated methodology and architecture include the existing InfluxDb database that is deployed inside a Trial Network, where every generated result is stored along with a minimum set of metadata. This approach is sufficient for filtering, parsing and generally processing the experimental data for given research. However, should an experimenter decide to share their results with a wider community, all part of the data contained in a Trial Network can be coupled with a Data Descriptor, where the experimenter can declare additional metadata for the results, and then exported to the Platform Central Repository.

Figure 6: Data reusability in 6G-SANDBOX

The Platform Central Repository is itself another InfluxDb database, ensuring direct compatibility, which stores a curated sub-set of all the measurements generated in the platform. Additionally, other useful artefacts, such as the original Trial Network Descriptor or references to used components can be stored in the centralized Artefacts Storage. This central storage provides longer term storage that is not dependent on the existence of the original Trial Network and allows experimenters to continue processing the data without consuming resources in the platform that could be useful for other experimenters.

The data contained in the Platform Central Repository is already structured and described thoroughly for basic processing and handling and can be made available using simple APIs. This data can be also used as the base for creating new datasets that can be exported to other data reusability solutions, such as Zenodo, SLICES-PP or a Data Space, provided that the experimenter includes the necessary information required for each ecosystem.

4 STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS.

4.1 INTRODUCTION AND INITIAL ANALYSIS.

The beyond 5G and 6G ecosystem is a complex network of interacting cross-industry actors who collaborate to define, build, and deliver value-creating solutions. This ecosystem has evolved from the linear value chains of previous generations to a more intricate value network, reflecting the technological advancements and changing market demands.

The Business Modelling, Ecosystem and Value creation sub-work group of the vision work group of the 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) has provided a categorisation of key stakeholders [11]. This ecosystem is characterized by its dynamic nature, with stakeholders often playing multiple roles and forming strategic partnerships to generate additional value. The ongoing softwarisation and disaggregation of

telecommunication technologies have further emphasized the relevance of this ecosystem approach for beyond 5G and 6G markets.

The European 5G community has been working on a partitioning of the ecosystem at large, since the middle of the 5G-PPP programme. While the latest revision, performed by the SNS OPS CSA³, is ongoing and considers the ecosystem evolution in SNS, an overarching approach is published in as depicted in Figure 7 and is primarily considering the “5G PPP provisioning ecosystem” that includes all stakeholders involved in technological development around 5G and beyond, and the “5G PPP users’ ecosystem” that includes all stakeholders who are using 5G technologies. “5G Enablers and Facilitators” are also considered as secondary entities, including generic roles such as Consultants, Business & Finance facilitators, Education and Community facilitators.

Figure 7: 5G PPP Ecosystems Interaction

4.2 THIRD-PARTY ROLES

Following the stakeholders’ ecosystem analysis, the prevailing third-party roles for the 6G SANDBOX developments, both in terms of the provisioning and user ecosystems analysis are presented in the sections that follow.

4.2.1 PROVISIONING ECOSYSTEM ACTORS

The provisioning ecosystem⁴ stakeholders are responsible for developing, delivering, and providing beyond 5G and 6G services. They include:

- Service Providers
- Network Operators
- Hardware and Software Suppliers
- Cloud Providers
- Datacentre Providers
- Solution Integrators

The provisioning ecosystem in the beyond 5G and 6G context is responsible for developing, delivering, and providing advanced telecommunication services. It includes key stakeholders such as Service Providers, Network Operators, Hardware and Software Suppliers, Cloud Providers, Datacentre Providers, and Solution Integrators. The provisioning ecosystem aims to address challenges like poor cost efficiencies and low flexibility in service delivery, while catering to the diverse requirements of enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC), and massive IoT (mIoT).

³ <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/csa-s/#SNS-OPS>

⁴ <https://bscw.5g-ppp.eu/pub/bscw.cgi/d528663/5GPPP-provisioning-ecosystem-02.pdf>

4.2.2 USER ECOSYSTEM ACTORS

The user ecosystem⁵ is multi-facet, and incorporates a wide set of relevant actors, including verticals industry and related associations, research, policy and SDOs.

4.2.2.1 VERTICAL ECOSYSTEM ACTORS

These stakeholders apply beyond 5G and 6G services in combination with other technologies to offer solutions to vertical customers and users. They include:

- Software Providers
- Data Processing and Hosting Providers
- Service Integrators
- Computer Consultancy firms
- Vertical sector-specific roles (e.g., industrial automation, healthcare, automotive)

Vertical Ecosystem Actors emerge as pivotal transformative agents, bridging advanced telecommunication capabilities with industry-specific requirements. These stakeholders are not passive consumers of network services, but active innovators who innovate by introducing advanced technological capabilities across diverse sectors. In this complex ecosystem software providers, data processing experts, and service integrators collaborate to create tailored solutions that transcend traditional connectivity paradigms. As examples, a healthcare technology company can work closely with network providers to develop ultra-low latency medical monitoring systems, while an automotive manufacturer designs autonomous vehicle communication platforms leveraging next-generation network capabilities.

The Vertical Ecosystem Actors are characterized by their deep domain expertise and their ability to translate complex technological potential into practical, sector-specific applications. They navigate the intricate intersection between advanced telecommunications and industry-specific challenges, creating value through customized solutions that address operational needs of the sectors.

4.2.2.2 RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

- Academic Institutions
- Research Organizations
- Standardization Bodies

The stakeholders in the research and development are at the forefront of innovation and collaboration in the evolving telecommunications landscape. Academic institutions and research organizations are driving fundamental research and technological advancements in all areas of beyond 5G and 6G. Standardization bodies are facilitating international cooperation and ensuring interoperability of 6G technologies.

4.2.2.3 GOVERNMENT AND REGULATORY BODIES

- Policy Makers
- Regulatory Agencies
- Funding Organizations

Government and Regulatory Bodies emerge as pivotal players, orchestrating the complex interplay of innovation, competition, and public interest. These entities, ranging from independent regulatory authorities to government ministries, serve as the guardians of fair play and technological progress in the telecommunications sector. In a world where spectrum is a finite resource, and the potential for technological advancement seems limitless, these bodies endeavour to establish the balance between fostering innovation and ensuring equitable

⁵ <https://bscw.5g-ppp.eu/pub/bscw.cgi/d528670/5GPPP-user-ecosystem-02.pdf>

access to resources, all while safeguarding consumer interests. These bodies are active shapers of the telecommunications ecosystem. They craft policies that set the stage for market competition, manage the precious commodity of radio spectrum, and establish the rules of engagement for service providers. Their decisions ripple through the industry, influencing everything from the rollout of new technologies to the affordability of services for end-users.

In this narrative of technological advancement, funding organisations play the role of enablers, facilitating the transformation of visionary concepts into tangible results. These entities, ranging from government agencies to private foundations and industry partners, form the financial backbone of cutting-edge telecommunications research. Their impact creates the fertile ground for transformative ideas to flourish and bridge the gap between academic pursuits and industry needs, ensuring that research remains relevant and impactful.

4.2.2.4 END USERS AND CUSTOMERS

- Enterprises across various sectors
- Individual consumers

As we move towards the beyond 5G and 6G era, the relationship between technology providers and end users will become more dynamic and collaborative, with user needs and experiences playing an increasingly central role in driving technological advancements and service innovations. However, a tussle exists between greater user participation in defining use cases, and the challenge to involve end users to anticipate their needs accurately, in view of the complexity of future technologies.

4.2.3 6G-SANDBOX ROLE IN THE ECOSYSTEM

6G-SANDBOX primarily falls into the Research and Development stakeholder group, with strong connections to other stakeholder categories. 6G-SANDBOX provides a comprehensive and modular facility for the European experimentation ecosystem, aligning with the core function of research infrastructures. The project brings together academic institutions, research organizations and industry partners, which is characteristic of major R&D initiatives. It aims to support technology and research validation processes needed in the pathway towards 6G, directly contributing to the 6G roadmap. By providing an open 6G experimentation environment, 6G-SANDBOX facilitates research and innovation across various stakeholders, including industry, SMEs, and academia, as demonstrated through the high interest of various stakeholders in the project's open calls.

The stakeholder groups of interest and of high relevance to 6G-SANDBOX are mainly:

- Industry Partners: The project emphasizes open access and reusability of results and components, suggesting strong relevance for industry partners and in particular SMEs, who can leverage the infrastructure for testing and developing 6G technologies.
- Provisioning Ecosystem Actors: The project incorporates advanced beyond 5G and 6G technologies, driven by a vision of end-to-end physical connectivity infrastructure, which is of particular interest to network operators, hardware and software suppliers, and solution integrators working on 6G technologies.
- Research and Development Stakeholders: The project aims to support technology and research validation processes needed in the pathway towards 6G, making it a precious resource for researchers and innovators in the field.
- Vertical Ecosystem Actors: 6G-SANDBOX aims to support the trial of 6G use cases, making it highly relevant for vertical industry players who want to experiment with and validate advanced telecommunications applications in their specific sectors.

4.3 ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

6G-SANDBOX published an engagement process and technical information for third party experimentation [9] in order to facilitate easier access to the infrastructure. In summary the aforementioned document describes

the comprehensive and modular trials facility for the European experimentation ecosystem, supporting technology and research validation processes needed for the development of 6G over the next decade. It streamlines the process of 6G experimentation by providing modular, automated, and easily deployable components and infrastructure.

4.3.1 PLATFORM DEPLOYMENT DESCRIPTION

It describes the defined and realised concept of Trial Networks, which are fully configurable, manageable, controllable and automatically deployable networks combining virtual, physical, and emulated resources [10]. The purpose of trial networks is to enable experiments to validate 6G technologies and measure key performance indicators (KPIs). A 6G Library contains software components that facilitate the modular and automatic deployment of Trial Networks. The 6G library follows the philosophy that each element in the library follows the “Everything as a Code” (EaC) approach, designed for easy deployment within the 6G-SANDBOX platform [10]. The components in the 6G library include software and hardware descriptors like Mobile Core, RAN/ORAN options, UE devices, TSN infrastructure, Satellite backhaul, emulators, and traffic generators. These components are accessible through a common API framework for interaction with third-party components and applications. A TNLCM manages the deployment and life cycle of trial networks, ensuring they are accessible and operational. The TNLCM orchestrates any actions needed to alter the state of a trial network. A set of predefined requirements and best practices ensures uniformity and seamless integration of components, which comply with tools like Terraform, Ansible, and Jenkins. Third parties can act as Trial Network Users (TNU), creating test cases, conducting measurements, and deploying applications. TNUs have easy access through portals for composing and conducting experiments, with secure API interactions through CAPIF.

4.3.2 DESCRIPTION OF TECHNOLOGY GAPS

The engagement process document addresses experimentation challenges of deploying an infrastructure which facilitates medium- to long-term experiments without frequent manual reconfiguration and giving experimenters access to internal network configuration.

A prerequisite for experimentation is the enrichment of the 6G library with software components as well as representation models of the physical components that reside at the four platforms deployed at the locations listed above. Through the enrichment of the 6G library, the TNLCM is becoming aware of the platform capabilities and the resource availability for each platform. Third parties can access the experimentation infrastructure through the trial networks portal, which allows them to set up a trial network. After setting up the trial network, they can use the selected experimentation life-cycle manager to run their experiment. A default experimentation life-cycle manager is provided; however, the use of other experimentation life-cycle managers is not excluded. Meant to create tangible and long-term impact, 6G KPIs and KVIs being quantified through the facility during the experiment, are made accessible to any interested party; while the set of developments and APIs, which are produced, are feeding an open repository as an initial step to move the contributions and the lessons learned beyond the project duration.

4.4 ESTABLISHED COLLABORATIONS

The established collaborations are contextualized through the interest of the stakeholder community in responding to the open calls of the project. Note though that additional collaborations have been established outside the scope of the open calls (Financial Support for Third Parties).

4.4.1 INVOLVEMENT OF STAKEHOLDERS IN OPEN CALLS

Finally, one of the 6G-SANDBOX goals is to prepare and implement the open calls, establishing a mechanism for third parties – accepted after the open call evaluations – to use the project 6G and experimental facilities. Three open calls have been organized for innovative experiments as well as for inclusion of new infrastructures and functionalities in the overall 6G-SANDBOX facility portfolio.

The participation of various types of organisations in the 6G-SANDBOX open calls, measured by numbers of received submissions, is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Open Call participants per type of organization.

Depending on the addressed open call topic – inclusion of new infrastructures and functionalities OR innovative experiments – the distribution of received submissions is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Participants per Open Call topic.

Figure 10: Participants per ecosystem actors.

Figure 10 considers the participation in the open calls in accordance with the actors’ structure presented above. The provisioning and vertical ecosystem actors as well as research and development players have been participating in the 6G-SANDBOX open calls almost with an even representation, whereas governmental and regulatory bodies as well as end users and customers have been not represented, as the open call participation is not suitable for these actors and not planned in the project.

More than 95% of the participants are from Europe, from EU member states and associated countries (Norway, Turkey, UK). Proposers from Kenya, South Africa, and Taiwan have been participated in the 6G-SANDBOX open calls as well.

4.4.2 INVOLVEMENT OF STAKEHOLDERS OUTSIDE THE OPEN CALLS

In Table 1, we present the 6G-SANDBOX collaborations beyond the project open calls, presented above, considering cooperation with other collaboration projects as well as discussing opportunities for experimentation with further community members and allowing experimentation / usage of 6G-SANDBOX facilities without funding provided by the project – so called “free experimentation”.

Project	Topic of cooperation
BeGreen	Energy in RAN
CENTRIC	AI air interface validation
6G-SHINE	Channel sounding
RIGOUROUS	Security
PRIVATEER	Security
TERRAMETA	High frequency - Channel Sounding at 140 and 300GHz
FIDAL	Re-use of 6G-SANDBOX open call methodology

Table 1: Collaborations outside of the Open Call process.

The 6G-SANDBOX has been discussing various experimentation opportunities with stakeholders from literally all targeted groups, presented in the previous section above. Because of privacy protection, we are not able to disclose names of involved organizations, but can present the main areas of discussions, as listed below:

- Deployment of a small cell loaner in UMA, to be used for the network densification in Malaga city centre
- Deployment of RIS in a parking lot to extend coverage in FR1
- Deployment of a film lens to increase FR2 beyond building window and glass
- Deploy transparent glass antenna on the small cells

- Deploy a few glasses antenna hidden to the public to improve coverage
- Loaners of VDI heads on demand for experiment and measurement campaign
- Loan of a RIS to expand RISFORCE project and measurement campaign
- Development of RIS driver
- Enabling JCAS via accessing ORAN CSI information
- AI receiver applied to base station, performance analysis
- Participate with the ORU to the CENTRIC demo with NVIDIA
- Run experimentation on ORAN for energy consumption

5 CONCLUSION

This document presents the results of the activities of Task 2.2 “Trial Networks Lifecycle and stakeholders analysis”, and is centered in the design of the components required for supporting the lifecycle of the Trial Networks and the management of experimental results. Implementation of this design is not covered by this document, since it will be reported as part of WP4 “Integration and management of 6G trial networks”.

With regards to Deliverable 2.2 “Final overall framework design and requirements” **Error! Reference source not found.**, this document provides additional details on the design and specifications of the Trial Network lifecycle (e.g., the TNLCM descriptor, the TN stages and the data reusability approach). In addition, the reader can find updates on the stakeholder’s analysis first introduced in Deliverable D2.1 “Ecosystem Analysis and 6G-SANDBOX Facility Design” [10]. Furthermore, the document describes the third-parties engagement strategy followed by the Project and it provides a view of the collaborations that the Project has established with several external entities at the time of writing.

6 REFERENCES

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ANNEX 1 – TRIAL NETWORK DESCRIPTOR EXAMPLE

```
trial_network:
  tn_init:
    type: "tn_init"
    dependencies: []
    input: {}
  vnet-internal:
    type: "vnet"
    name: "internal"
    dependencies:
      - "tn_init"
    input:
      one_vnet_first_ip: "10.10.10.1"
      one_vnet_netmask: 24
      one_vnet_address_size: 100
      one_vnet_gw: "10.10.10.1"
      one_vnet_dns: "1.1.1.1"
  oneKE-cluster:
    type: "oneKE"
    name: "cluster"
    dependencies:
      - "tn_init"
      - "vnet-internal"
    input:
      one_oneKE_external_vnet: "tn_vxlan"
      one_oneKE_internal_vnet: "vnet-internal"
      one_oneKE_version: "129"
      one_oneKE_multus: "YES"
      one_oneKE_cni_plugin: "canal"
      one_oneKE_cilium_range: ""
      one_oneKE_longhorn: "YES"
      one_oneKE_metallb: "YES"
      one_oneKE_metallb_range: "10.10.10.200-10.10.10.240"
      one_oneKE_traefik: "NO"
      one_oneKE_dns: "1.1.1.1 8.8.8.8"
  open5gs_k8s-core:
    type: "open5gs_k8s"
    name: "core"
    dependencies:
      - "oneKE-cluster"
    input:
      one_open5gs_k8s_target: "oneKE-cluster"
      one_open5gs_k8s_mcc: "214"
      one_open5gs_k8s_mnc: "702"
      one_open5gs_k8s_apn: "internet"
      one_open5gs_k8s_tac: 1
      one_open5gs_k8s_s_nssai_sst: 1
      one_open5gs_k8s_s_nssai_sd: "000009"
      one_open5gs_k8s_amf_ip: "10.10.10.200"
      one_open5gs_k8s_upf_ip: "10.10.10.201"
      one_open5gs_k8s_ue_count: 1
  ueransim-gnb:
    type: "ueransim"
    name: "gnb"
    dependencies:
      - "tn_init"
      - "open5gs_k8s-core"
```

input:

```
one_ueransim_networks:  
  - "tn_vxlan"  
one_ueransim_run_gnb: "YES"  
one_ueransim_run_ue: "NO"  
one_ueransim_gnb_linked_open5gs: "open5gs_k8s-core"  
one_ueransim_gnb_proxy: ""  
one_ueransim_gnb_mcc: "001"  
one_ueransim_gnb_mnc: "01"  
one_ueransim_gnb_tac: 200  
one_ueransim_gnb_amf_address: "10.10.10.200"  
one_ueransim_gnb_slices_sst: 1  
one_ueransim_gnb_slices_sd: "000001"
```

ueransim-ue:

```
type: "ueransim"  
name: "ue"  
dependencies:  
  - "tn_init"  
  - "open5gs_k8s-core"  
  - "ueransim-gnb"
```

input:

```
one_ueransim_networks:  
  - "tn_vxlan"  
one_ueransim_run_gnb: "NO"  
one_ueransim_run_ue: "YES"  
one_ueransim_ue_linked_gnb: "ueransim-gnb"  
one_ueransim_ue_supl: "imsi-001010000000001"  
one_ueransim_ue_mcc: "001"  
one_ueransim_ue_mnc: "01"  
one_ueransim_ue_key: "465B5CE8B199B49FAA5F0A2EE238A6BC"  
one_ueransim_ue_op: "E8ED289DEBA952E4283B54E88E6183CA"  
one_ueransim_ue_gnbSearchList: ""  
one_ueransim_ue_session_apn: "internet"  
one_ueransim_ue_session_sst: 1  
one_ueransim_ue_session_sd: "000001"  
one_ueransim_ue_configured_nssai_sst: 1  
one_ueransim_ue_configured_nssai_sd: "000001"  
one_ueransim_ue_default_nssai_sst: 1  
one_ueransim_ue_default_nssai_sd: "000001"
```